

CORE-BEHAVIORAL COMPETENCIES, TEACHING CAPABILITIES AND PERFORMANCE: BASIS FOR INSTITUTIONAL ENHANCEMENT PLAN

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Core-Behavioral Competencies, Teaching Capabilities and Performance: Basis for Institutional Enhancement Plan

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Abstract

This study on core behavioral competencies, teaching capability, and performance is related to different literature and studies. The core behavioral competencies of a teacher include self-management, professionalism and ethics, result focus, teamwork, service orientation and innovations. On the other hand, capability assessment focused on content knowledge and pedagogy, learning environment and diversity of learners, curriculum and planning, assessment and reporting and plus factor. Finally, the Department of Education has its electronic version of self-assessment tool for Result-based Management System (RPMS). This provided an overall picture of the teachers' strengths and needs which will be used in the planning for the next school year. The data reflected the performance of the teachers used as one of the bases for promotion and designation. This study set out to determine the level of teachers' demographic profile, which showed result that there were more female teachers than male teachers in public schools. It simply implied that female teachers made up a larger part of educators despite the equal opportunity for both genders in the said profession, and largely because female teachers were pursuing teaching at far greater costs than male teachers do. This explained the fallacy that entailed education where Gender norms traverse a relatively female-dominated profession. Also, a significant high result has shown in the level of core behavioral competencies of the teachers that exhibited the greatest number of indicators in Professionalism and Ethics, followed by Self-Management, Teamwork, Results Focus, and Service Orientation. On the other perspective, teachers achieved a low result in Innovation. In self-management, it indicated that female teachers have significantly greater levels of self-management than their male colleagues. In DepEd Schools Division of Himamaylan City, teachers were required to have this performance review every end of the school year by rating their performances based on criteria set forth by the DepEd. With this, teachers were accomplishing this Individual performance, Commitment and Review Form (IPCRF) together with the Electronic Self-Assessment Tool (ESAT) as basis of their performances in schools. The institutional improvement plan has been crafted to help improve the rating performance of the teachers in the identified districts.

Keywords: core behavioral competencies, teaching capability, performance

Introduction

People viewed school as an institution where competent individuals were training young ones for independence, aspiring for the betterment of their client's living conditions as well as their professional development.

Moreover, teaching performance was determined by one's knowledge, skills, and attitudes through active involvement in various in-service pieces of training and programs, which can be monitored continuously in terms of their progress in the teaching standards using self-assessment to help them meet the required competence toward improving their teaching performance (Madrigal et al., 2019).

In 2015, the Department of Education issued guidelines on the establishment and implementation of the Results-based Performance Management System (RPMS) to ensure efficient, timely, and quality performance among personnel (DO No.2, s. 2015)

As a result, teaching standards in competence and performance of basic education teachers were proficient and satisfactory, and a relationship between the level of teaching standards competence and performance was observed. (Madrigal et al., 2019)

However, Barrogo (2019) revealed in his study that Key Result Areas (KRA) such as content knowledge and pedagogy are moderately difficult to achieve while curriculum and planning are very difficult to accomplish and achieved.

Difficulties in terms of accomplishing these objectives were commonly felt in actual teaching, especially in this time of pandemic when teachers struggle with distance learning while maintaining excellence and competence in implementing their teaching process.

In DepEd Schools Division of Himamaylan City, teachers were required to have this performance review every end of the school year by rating their performances based on criteria set forth by the DepEd. With this, teachers were accomplishing this Individual performance, Commitment and Review Form (IPCRF) together with the Electronic Self-Assessment Tool (ESAT) as basis of their performances in schools.

To address the gap, it was significant to know the teachers' recent Core Behavioral Competency rating and teaching capability results, in order to devise an Institutional Enhancement Plan to set up changes for the needs of school in improving the student's level of achievement and determining the needs necessary for the improvement of the school.

This study focused on assessing the Core Behavioral Competencies, Teaching Capabilities, and Performance as a basis for an Institutional Enhancement Plan.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the core behavioral competencies, teaching capabilities, and performance, basis for an institutional enhancement plan. Specifically, it aimed to answer the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the teachers in terms of the following:
 - 1.1. sex;
 - 1.2. position; and
 - 1.3. highest educational qualification?
2. What is the level of core behavioral competencies of the teachers in terms of:
 - 2.1. self-management;
 - 2.2. professionalism;
 - 2.3. result-focus;
 - 2.4. teamwork;
 - 2.5. service oriented; and
 - 2.6. innovation?
3. What is the teaching performance of the teachers in terms of:
 - 3.1. KRA1-Content Knowledge and Pedagogy;
 - 3.2. KRA2-Learning Environment and Diversity of Learners;
 - 3.3. KRA3-Curriculum and Planning;
 - 3.4. KRA4-Assessment and Reporting; and
 - 3.5. KRA5-Plus Factor?
4. Is there a significant difference in the level of core behavioral competence when grouped by profile?
5. Is there a significant relationship between teaching performance and the level of core behavioral competencies?
6. What institutional enhancement plan may be developed?

Methodology

Research Design

The research design that was deemed appropriate to this study was descriptive correlational research design. It aimed to describe a population, situation or phenomenon accurately and systematically. It answered what, when, where when and how questions (McCombes, 2020). She added that descriptive research was a design which can be used a wide variety of quantitative and qualitative methods to investigate one or more variables. It was an appropriate design due to its nature of collecting and interpreting data about the Core Behavioral Competencies, Teaching Capabilities and Performance of the teachers in Clusters 1-5 in the Schools Division of Himamaylan City.

Respondents

Schools Division of Himamaylan City has a population of 337 elementary teachers from Clusters 1 to 5 and the sample respondents has a total of 184 elementary teachers which were computed using the Slovin's formula ($n=N/1+Ne2$).

The table 1 below showed the distribution of the respondents per Cluster.

Table 1. Distribution of the Respondents per Cluster

Cluster	Teachers – respondents' population	Percentage
1	52	28.26
2	37	20.11
3	60	32.61
4	30	16.30
5	5	02.72
Total	184	100.00

The respondents of the study were the 184 teachers from the 5 Cluster of Schools Division of Himamaylan City. In determining the teacher respondents per Cluster, the researcher implemented simple random sampling utilizing the fishbowl method on each of the Cluster to identify the required number of teachers as mentioned on the table above. In detail, the researcher prepared numbers in a paper strip which correspond to the item or list of teachers per district. It should be mixed and randomly pick up paper strips based on the stated number of teachers per Cluster until you get the total number of respondents stated in the table above.

Instruments

Due to the nature of this study of collecting secondary data, the researcher utilized the results from Electronic Self-Assessment Tool (E-SAT), Result-based Performance Management System (RPMS) and Individual Performance Commitment and Review form (IPCR) as rated by the teachers in the school year 2019-2020. To collect all the data, researcher used of communication letter as a means of

asking permission to get the following data from the person-in-charge of the office.

Validity and Reliability of the Instrument

To gather all the necessary information needed to satisfy the objectives of the study, the researcher utilized secondary data from the Division Office through a letter communication. Thus, validity and reliability were not necessary in this study.

Procedure

Before the actual conduct of the study, the approval from the thesis committee have been accomplished, complying all the recommendations of the panel members approved by the Dean of Central Philippines State University – Graduate School. Next, a letter asking for permission has been sent to the School’s Division Superintendent to conduct the study. Also, a letter has been sent to the person-in-charge of the Division and District Supervisors asking for the data needed to satisfy the objectives of the study. Ensuring that the ethical procedures has been strictly followed in the entire duration of the research conduct.

The gathered data has been subjected for processing and computation for the analysis and interpretation through the use of SPSS. Likewise, the statistical tables has been constructed as per consideration to the objectives stated in this study. Finally, the results have been gathered and interpreted for relationship which lead to a formulation of the conclusions of the study which aimed to determine the Core Behavioral Competencies, Teaching Capabilities and Performance as Basis for the Institutional Improvement Plan in five Clusters of the Schools Division of Himamaylan City.

Data Analysis

The data analysis of this study agreed with the sequence of the objectives. Each question was associated with a statistical tool for descriptive and inferential interpretation respectively.

1. To determine the profile of the teachers such as sex, Position and Highest Educational Qualification, the Percentage Count and Percentage Distribution have been applied.
2. To determine the level of core behavioral competencies of the teachers in terms of Self-Management, Professionalism, Result-Focus, Teamwork, Service Oriented and Innovation, the mean have been used.
3. To determine the teaching performance of the teachers in terms such as KRA1-Content Knowledge and Pedagogy, KRA2-Learning Environment and Diversity of Learners, KRA3-Curriculum and Planning, KRA4-Assessment and Reporting and KRA5-Plus Factor, the weighted mean have been utilized.
4. To determine the significant difference on the level of Core Behavioral Competence when grouped by profile, Kruskal Wallis have been utilized.
5. To determine the significant relationship between the teaching performance and level of core behavioral competencies, the Spearman Rho have been utilized.

Ethical Considerations

The research panelists’ and professor's approval of the data collection strategy and tool guarantees that consent has been obtained and that ethical standards will be properly followed. Under the direction of the professor and panelists, a participant who will be selected and will be given approval to participate based on informed permission was asked to give their full consent.

As soon as the consent form is presented, the procedure for data collection will be followed. The study's objectives will be explained to the participants in reference to their voluntarily participating in it, and they will be made aware that they might leave at any time. They will be given guarantees that all information gathered throughout the study's design will be used only for academic and research endeavors, under the code name, and without taking the participant’s identities into consideration. Also, confidentiality will be discussed. Republic Act 10173 requires that any personally identifiable information voluntarily provided by participants be kept confidential and not used in a way that is against the Data Privacy Act.

Results and Discussion

This section presented the results based on the data gathered. Results were presented based on the order of the research objectives. The list of the interview responses was integrated in the discussion to provide context. Literature and studies were also included to ground the findings based on existing knowledge.

The Demographic Profile of Teachers

The demographic profile of teachers covered districts 1 to 5. Based on the data, there were 184 teachers involved in the study. In terms of sex, the group has more females than males. Most of the respondents were Teacher 1; followed in number by Teacher 2, Teacher 3, Master Teacher I, and Master Teacher 2. In terms of the respondents’ highest educational attainment, it was mostly bachelor’s degrees; followed in number by master’s degrees, and doctorate degrees.

These sets of data affirmed the claim of Regalado (2017) that female teachers were more than male teachers in public schools. The profile data was also consistent with the data posted by dela Fuente (2020) that in terms of teaching positions, most teachers were Teacher I. Uayan et al. (2020) reported that most teachers in their research have bachelor's degrees as the highest educational attainment, which was similar to the finding in this paper.

Based on the data gathered, it simply implied that female teachers make up a larger part of educators despite the equal opportunity for both genders in the said profession, and largely because female teachers were pursuing teaching at far greater costs than male teachers do. This explained the fallacy that entailed education where Gender norms traverse a relatively female-dominated profession.

Table 2. Teachers' Demographic Profile

<i>Sex</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Male	20	10.9
Female	164	89.1
<i>Positions</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Teacher 1	132	71.7
Teacher 2	24	13.0
Teacher 3	18	9.8
Master Teacher 1	8	4.3
Master Teacher 2	2	1.1
<i>Educational Attainment</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Bachelor's degree	173	94.0
Master's degree	10	5.4
Doctorate degree	1	.5
Total	184	100.0

The level of Core Behavioral Competencies of the Teachers

The teachers' degree of core behavioral competencies included: self-management, professionalism and ethics, results focus, teamwork, service orientation, and innovation. Teachers demonstrated the greatest number of indicators in professionalism and ethics which was very high. This was followed respectively by: Self-Management, Teamwork, Results Focus, and service orientation which were very high. On the other hand, teachers achieved the least number of competencies in Innovation which was high.

Teachers scored high in professionalism and ethics, which may be attributed to the assumption written by Jayson Bajar et al. (2020) that these were inseparable from teachers because the expectations for them were greater moral and ethical standards.

Innovations were supported by an interview where master teachers failed to mention innovation as something that can be observed in teachers. The interview also suggested that innovation was a competency given less attention not until the pandemic when teachers are compelled to innovate instructional adjustments for engagement and responsiveness. The interviewees also mentioned that the other competencies are manifested by teachers in their efficient submissions, collaboration, responsible attendance and punctuality, flexibility, and goal-setting as early as Brigada Eskwela.

This only implied that innovation will not transpire in oblivion but rather demands openness and communication within the organization. This was very likely to take place in education, where institutions cannot be left alone to undertake difficult processes of transformation, but also need to foster support from teachers throughout the developing world of genuine innovation.

Table 3. The level of Core Behavioral Competencies of the Teachers

<i>Behavioral Competencies</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Self-Management	4.61	.644	Very High
Professionalism and Ethics	4.78	.475	Very High
Results Focus	4.29	.692	Very High
Teamwork	4.55	.634	Very High
Service Orientation	4.23	.763	Very High
Innovation	3.70	1.094	High

Note: 4.21 – 5.000: Very High; 3.41 – 4.20 High; 2.61 – 3.40 Average; 1.81 – 2.60 Low; 1.00-1.80 Very Low

The Teaching Performance of the Teachers

These KRA's were considered as the baseline of the expected performances that a teacher should possess. Teachers' level of performance according to the five key result areas as presented in the table. Teachers performed best at KRA 4: Assessment and Reporting with an outstanding rating. This was followed respectively by KRA 2: Learning Environment and Diversity of Learners with also an Outstanding rating, KRA 3: Curriculum and Planning with Very Satisfactory rating, KRA 1: Content Knowledge and Pedagogy with Very Satisfactory rating, and KRA 5: Plus Factor with Very Satisfactory rating. These findings were not consistent with the report of Lacayanga (2019), where KRA 3: Curriculum and Planning was the most difficult to attain and KRA 5: Plus Factor was the easiest to attain. This may be attributed to differences in the studies' context.

As per interview responses, teachers scored high in Assessment and Reporting may be attributed to the shared responses that teachers were always prompt in submitting reports. Master teachers mentioned that teachers were diligently, adaptively performing their responsibilities according to the needs of learners.

KRA 5: Plus Factor having the lowest average may be attributed to a response that emerged from the interview that teachers have to go beyond their actual duties and responsibilities to score higher in this component. The master teachers specified coordinatorship, extra-curricular participation, project development, and innovation—which were a competency where teachers also got the lowest in the Core Behavioral Competencies portion of this discussion.

Table 4. *Teaching performance of the teachers*

Key Result Areas	Mean	SD	Interpretation
KRA 1: Content Knowledge and Pedagogy	4.61	.644	Very High
KRA 2: Learning Environment and Diversity of Learners	4.78	.475	Very High
KRA 3: Curriculum and Planning	4.29	.692	Very High
KRA 4: Assessment and Reporting	4.55	.634	Very High
KRA 5: Plus Factor	4.23	.763	Very High
Key Result Areas	3.70	1.094	High

Note: 4.500 – 5.000: Outstanding; 3.500 – 4.499: Very Satisfactory; 2.500 – 3.499: Satisfactory; 1.50 – 2.499 Unsatisfactory Below 1.499 Poor

The Significant Difference in the Level of Core Behavioral Competencies when grouped by Sex.

As shown in table 5, the significant difference in the level of core behavioral competence when grouped by sex. This clarified the relationship between male and female teachers in terms of the level of Core Behavioral Competencies. To further support this study, specifically in the level of Core Behavioral Competencies according to profile variables, Mann-Whitney U test was used to test the null hypothesis that there was no significant difference in the level of core behavioral competence when grouped by sex, as shown in Table 5. At the 5% level of significance, results revealed that there was a significant difference in the level of core behavioral competence in terms of self-management between male and female teachers. This suggested that female teachers have significantly higher levels of self-management than their male counterparts.

On the other hand, there was no significant difference in the level of core behavioral competence in terms of professionalism and ethics, results focus, teamwork, service orientation, and innovation between male and female teachers. This suggested that both male and female teachers have the same level of competence in the aforementioned areas.

These findings mostly supported by Madrigal et al. (2019)'s finding that there was no significant difference in the competence of teachers when grouped according to sex. Moreover, the actuality of significant differences in one component was consistent with the finding that females have higher self-regulation than males as reported by Zhonggen Yu (2021). In addition to this, Maryam Meshkat and Reza Nejati (2017) found that females have higher self-awareness than males. This suggests that differences between achieving male and female teachers showed up on a larger scale, and project significant variation in terms of group levels. As we continue to comprehend the learning process, self-regulation and self-awareness were vital for educational practice as this should be evident in the mind-set of an educator having an important role in motivating students towards self-improvement and academic excellence.

Table 5. *Significant Difference in the Level of Core Behavioral Competence when grouped by Sex*

Variable	Test Stat	P-Value	Decision for Ho	Conclusion
Self-Management Male (Mean Rank = 70.10) Female (Mean Rank = 95.23)	1192.000	.014	Reject Ho	Significant
Professionalism and Ethics Male (Mean Rank = 90.35) Female (Mean Rank = 92.76)	1597.000	.779	Do not reject Ho	Not significant
Results Focus Male (Mean Rank = 91.13) Female (Mean Rank = 92.67)	1612.500	.893	Do not reject Ho	Not significant
Teamwork Male (Mean Rank = 92.08) Female (Mean Rank = 92.55)	1631.500	.965	Do not reject Ho	Not significant
Service Orientation Male (Mean Rank = 85.05) Female (Mean Rank = 93.41)	1491.000	.475	Do not reject Ho	Not significant
Innovation Male (Mean Rank = 93.30) Female (Mean Rank = 92.40)	1624.000	.941	Do not reject Ho	Not significant

Note: Highly Significant if p-value is lesser than 0.01, Significant if p-value is lesser than 0.05, Not Significant is greater than 0.05

The Significant Difference in the Level of Core Behavioral Competencies when grouped by Position

This pertained in the significant difference on the level of core behavioral competencies when grouped by position. Kruskal Wallis H test was utilized to assess the null hypothesis that there is no significant difference on the level of core behavioral competence when grouped by position, as presented in Table 6. At the 5% level of significance, results revealed that there was a significant difference in the level of core behavioral competence in terms of innovation when grouped by the teachers' position. Pairwise, comparison revealed that Master Teacher 2 has a significantly higher level of innovation than other positions. On the other hand, there was no significant difference on the level of core behavioral competence in terms of self-management, professionalism and ethics, results focus, teamwork, and service orientation of teachers when grouped by position. This suggested that both teachers have the same level of competence in the aforementioned areas regardless of position.

In DepEd's organization, master teacher II functioned as a higher instructional leader. Thus, the significant difference existing only in the core behavioral competency, innovation, was supported by Slimane (2015)'s claim that leaders were needed to have innovative skills. Interestingly, however, the second highest average in Innovation belongs to Teacher I. This may be attributed to the idea that these were teachers who were dominantly, relatively new to the profession. With this, these teachers may have been exposed to emerging perspectives and novel approaches.

The facts gathered simply implied that real challenges happening in every institution were not on ways of improvement but rather on sustaining on what was embedded in the educational system. Teachers practicing their profession for many years were constrained by their already adjusted routine, though age explained very little about actual performance in society, countless innovators were taken from the younger generation where a flush of ideas were obviously vibrant and was visible in every learning innovation.

Table 6. Significant difference in the Level of Core Behavioral Competence when grouped by Position

Variable	Test Stat	P-Value	Decision for h0	Conclusion
Self-Management	6.540	.162	Do not reject Ho	Not significant
<i>Teacher 1 (Mean Rank = 89.11)</i> <i>Teacher 2 (Mean Rank = 89.00)</i> <i>Teacher 3 (Mean Rank = 111.17)</i> <i>Master Teacher 1 (Mean Rank = 110.00)</i> <i>Master Teacher 2 (Mean Rank = 120.50)</i>				
Variable	Test Stat	P-Value	Decision for h0	Conclusion
Professionalism and Ethics	1.726	.786	Do not reject Ho	Not significant
<i>Teacher 1 (Mean Rank = 91.03)</i> <i>Teacher 2 (Mean Rank = 98.81)</i> <i>Teacher 3 (Mean Rank = 90.11)</i> <i>Master Teacher 1 (Mean Rank = 98.81)</i> <i>Master Teacher 2 (Mean Rank = 110.00)</i>				
Variable	Test Stat	P-Value	Decision for h0	Conclusion
Results Focus	4.148	.386	Do not reject Ho	Not significant
<i>Teacher 1 (Mean Rank = 91.73)</i> <i>Teacher 2 (Mean Rank = 83.50)</i> <i>Teacher 3 (Mean Rank = 98.33)</i> <i>Master Teacher 1 (Mean Rank = 105.75)</i> <i>Master Teacher 2 (Mean Rank = 146.00)</i>				
Variable	Test Stat	P-Value	Decision for h0	Conclusion
Teamwork	4.817	.307	Do not reject Ho	Not significant
<i>Teacher 1 (Mean Rank = 89.09)</i> <i>Teacher 2 (Mean Rank = 93.69)</i> <i>Teacher 3 (Mean Rank = 101.47)</i> <i>Master Teacher 1 (Mean Rank = 116.38)</i> <i>Master Teacher 2 (Mean Rank = 127.00)</i>				
Variable	Test Stat	P-Value	Decision for h0	Conclusion
Service Orientation	7.879	.096	Do not reject Ho	Not significant
<i>Teacher 1 (Mean Rank = 92.76)</i> <i>Teacher 2 (Mean Rank = 73.04)</i> <i>Teacher 3 (Mean Rank = 102.42)</i> <i>Master Teacher 1 (Mean Rank = 111.00)</i> <i>Master Teacher 2 (Mean Rank = 145.50)</i>				
Variable	Test Stat	P-Value	Decision for h0	Conclusion
Innovation	15.031	.005	Reject Ho	Significant
<i>Teacher 1 (Mean Rank = 99.54)</i> <i>Teacher 2 (Mean Rank = 68.50)</i> <i>Teacher 3 (Mean Rank = 67.61)</i> <i>Master Teacher 1 (Mean Rank = 88.50)</i> <i>Master Teacher 2 (Mean Rank = 156.00)</i>				

Note: Highly Significant if p-value is lesser than 0.01; Significant if p-value is lesser than 0.05; Not Significant is greater than 0.05

The Significant Difference in the Level of Core Behavioural Competence when grouped by Highest Educational Attainment

This pertained in the significant difference on the level of core behavioural competence when grouped by Highest Educational Attainment. Kruskal Wallis H test was used to test the null hypothesis that there was no significant difference on the level of core behavioral competence when categorized by highest educational attainment, as shown in Table 7. At the 5% level of significance, results uncovered that there was no significant difference in the level of core behavioral competence in terms of self-management, professionalism and ethics, results focus, teamwork, service orientation, and innovation.

This was inconsistent with the finding of Thomas Ng and Daniel Feldman (2009) that education level was positively related to behaviors and that of Abun et al. (2021), claiming that a significant difference existed in the behaviors of employees based on educational attainment.

To provide context, however, the interview responses revealed that regardless of the educational attainment, the teachers were geared towards learner-centered behaviors which are specified in DepEd’s core behavioral competencies: “biskan doctorate, you need to study the level of the learners (even if you earn a doctorate degree, you need to study the level of the learners)”.

This only showed that educational attainment was not highly associated with how a teacher should understand and connect with learners and even co-workers, as educational attainment does not fully address whether such a level of achievement could generate a high achieving individual or exert a positive influence on others on the accumulation of learning and other educational advantages.

Table 7. Significant difference in the Level of Core Behavioral Competence when grouped by Highest Educational Attainment

Variable	Test Stat	P-Value	Decision for H0	Conclusion
Self-Management	1.163	.559	Do not reject Ho	Not significant
<i>Bachelor's degree (Mean Rank = 91.69)</i>				
<i>Master's degree (Mean Rank = 103.70)</i>				
<i>Doctorate degree (Mean Rank = 120.50)</i>				
Variable	Test Stat	P-Value	Decision for H0	Conclusion
Professionalism and Ethics	.234	.889	Do not reject Ho	Not significant
<i>Bachelor's degree (Mean Rank = 92.42)</i>				
<i>Master's degree (Mean Rank = 92.10)</i>				
<i>Doctorate degree (Mean Rank = 110.00)</i>				
Variable	Test Stat	P-Value	Decision for H0	Conclusion
Results Focus	1.368	.505	Do not reject Ho	Not significant
<i>Bachelor's degree (Mean Rank = 91.88)</i>				
<i>Master's degree (Mean Rank = 97.90)</i>				
<i>Doctorate degree (Mean Rank = 146.00)</i>				
Variable	Test Stat	P-Value	Decision for H0	Conclusion
Teamwork	.747	.688	Do not reject Ho	Not significant
<i>Bachelor's degree (Mean Rank = 91.98)</i>				
<i>Master's degree (Mean Rank = 98.05)</i>				
<i>Doctorate degree (Mean Rank = 127.00)</i>				
Variable	Test Stat	P-Value	Decision for H0	Conclusion
Service Orientation	2.600	.273	Do not reject Ho	Not significant
<i>Bachelor's degree (Mean Rank = 91.16)</i>				
<i>Master's degree (Mean Rank = 110.45)</i>				
<i>Doctorate degree (Mean Rank = 145.50)</i>				
Variable	Test Stat	P-Value	Decision for H0	Conclusion
Innovation	5.055	.080	Do not reject Ho	Not significant
<i>Bachelor's degree (Mean Rank = 90.44)</i>				
<i>Master's degree (Mean Rank = 121.80)</i>				
<i>Doctorate degree (Mean Rank = 156.00)</i>				

Note: Highly Significant if p-value is lesser than 0.01, Significant if p-value is lesser than 0.05, Not Significant is greater than 0.05

Presents the relationship between the Teaching Performance and Level of Core Behavioral Competencies

This pertained in the relationships between Teaching Performance and the Level of Core Behavioral Competencies. Spearman’s rho was used to characterize the relationship between teaching performance and level of core behavioral competencies, as presented in Table 8. Results showed that there was a weak significant correlation between teaching performance and level of core behavioral competencies in terms of results focus. The positive correlation implied that the higher the teaching performance, the higher the level of results-focus and vice versa. This was consistent with the claim of Odindo et al. (2020) that goal setting was positively correlated to teacher performance.

Moreover, there was a positive significant relationship between performance and level of core behavioral competencies in terms of service orientation. The higher the teaching performance, the higher the level of service orientation and vice versa. This was supported by the study of Wieslaw Urban (2009) reporting that service orientation affects performance.

Also, there was a positive significant relationship between performance and level of core behavioral competencies in terms of teamwork. The higher the teaching performance, the higher the level of teamwork and vice versa. This affirmed Akiba and Liang (2016), claimed that teacher collaboration improved teacher quality.

The gathered data implied that collaboration played an important role in creating an effective educator in the field and improving student outcomes. A higher level of collaboration and effectiveness created an atmosphere of mutual trust that fueled teachers themselves, seeking to reduce division within the organization.

Table 8. Relationship between the Teaching Performance and Level of Core Behavioral Competencies

Variable	<i>rho</i>	<i>p-value</i>	Strength	Decision for <i>H0</i>	Conclusion
Teaching Performance and Self-Management	.071	.341	Weak	Do not reject <i>H0</i>	Not Significant
Teaching Performance and Professionalism and Ethics	.010	.898	Weak	Do not reject <i>H0</i>	Not Significant
Teaching Performance and Results Focus	.237	.001	Weak	Reject <i>H0</i>	Highly Significant
Teaching Performance and Teamwork	.162	.028	Weak	Reject <i>H0</i>	Significant
Teaching Performance and Service Orientation	.206	.005	Weak	Reject <i>H0</i>	Highly Significant
Teaching Performance and Innovation	.133	.071	Weak	Do not reject <i>H0</i>	Not Significant

Note: Highly Significant if the p-value is lesser than 0.01, Significant if the p-value is lesser than 0.05, Not Significant is greater than 0.05

Conclusion

This study set out to determine the level of teachers' demographic profile, which showed result that there were more female teachers than male teachers in public schools. Also, a significant high result has shown in the level of core behavioral competencies of the teachers that exhibited the greatest number of indicators in Professionalism and Ethics, followed by Self-Management, Teamwork, Results Focus, and Service Orientation. On the other perspective, teachers achieved a low result in Innovation. These suggested that innovation has to be given priority in the institutional development plan; also, teachers gave priority to living up to the greater moral and ethical standards expected of them.

Female teachers made up a larger part of educators despite the equal opportunity for both genders in the said profession, and largely because female teachers were pursuing teaching at far greater costs than male teachers do. This also explained the fallacy that entailed in education where gender norms traversed a relatively female-dominated profession.

In self-management, it indicated that female teachers have significantly greater levels of self-management than their male colleagues. This suggested that regardless of sex, we should do our task as an educator as to the fulfilment of our mission as educators in the field. Also, in terms of teaching positions, both teachers have the same level of competence in the aforementioned areas regardless of position.

Teacher's educational attainment should not be considered as a basis in determining the level of their behavioral competencies; also, female teachers were better at Self-Management than males, and that female and male teachers perform similarly in terms of Professionalism and Ethics, Results Focus, Teamwork, Service Orientation, and Innovation.

As we continue to comprehend the learning process, self-regulation and self-awareness were vital for educational practice as this should be evident in the mind-set of an educator having an important role in motivating students towards self-improvement and academic excellence. Also, a higher level of collaboration and effectiveness created an atmosphere of mutual trust that fuelled teachers themselves, seeking to reduce division within the organization.

Based on the results presented in the study, the researcher recommended the following to improve teachers' performance:

With all these, the researcher recommends for the schools and the division office to integrate Innovation in teacher-training. Speakers and facilitators for these training have to be Master Teacher 2.

In sessions on Self-Management, schools and the division office have to consider including sharing of best practices in terms of sex groups. Due to the positive correlation, they must also give attention to teaching performance, results focus, and service orientation to improve the levels of these components.

The researcher recommended schools to create a proactive, enduring, holistic-learning-based framework founded on inspirational, supportive strategies in creating institutional improvement plans prioritizing the aforementioned components. The division office may also create a framework like this for future teacher-training.

Teachers are recommended to constantly assess themselves and actively take part in their personal and professional improvement, especially in the components that they consider to be areas of priority.

They have to constantly communicate their professional development needs to their heads to inform them of the priorities to be integrated into teacher training every school year or quarter, through the perspective of the suggested framework based on the themes. They have to also establish inspiring collaborations with fellow teachers.

Teachers regardless of sex, Teaching positions, and highest educational attainment should perform well to cater the needs of the learners in having this passion in the teaching and learning process..

References

Caena, F. (n.d.). Directorate-general for Education and Culture Lifelong Learning: Policies and Programme School Education; Comenius Education and Training 2020 Thematic Working Group “professional Development of Teachers” Literature Review Quality in Teachers’ Continuing Professional Development.

Definition of Behavioural Competency. (2020). The Economic Times. <https://economictimes.indiatimes.com/definition/behavioural-competency>

DO 2, s. 2015. (2015). Guidelines on the establishment and implementation of the results-based performance management system (RPMS) in the Department of Education. Department of Education. <https://www.deped.gov.ph/2015/02/06/do-2-s-2015-guidelines-on-the-establishment-and-implementation-of-the-results-based-performance-management-system-rpms-in-the-department-of-education/>

DO 32, s. 2009. (n.d.). National Adoption and Implementation of NCBTS-TSNA and IPPD for Teachers, and Integration of its System Operations in the Overall Program for Continuing Teacher Capacity Building. Schools Division of South Cotabato | Department of Education. <https://depedsouthcotabato.org/wp-content/uploads/2019/03/e-SAT-Manual.pdf>

DO 32,s.2011. (n.d.). Policies Guidelines on Training and Development (T&D)Programs and Activities. Department of Education. https://www.deped.gov.ph/wp-content/uploads/2011/03/DO_s2011_32.pdf

Education Improvement Commission. (2020). School Improvement Plan Handbook. <https://www.edu.gov.on.ca/eng/document/reports/sihande.pdf>

Fallahi, A., Shahrabaki, B. N., Shahoei, R., Aala, F., & Ahmadi, S. M. (2019). Exploring the Components of Professional Ethics in Teaching, from the Perspective of Faculty Members in Iran. *Health Education & Health Promotion*, 7(2), 95–102. <https://doi.org/10.29252/hehp.7.2.95>

Farahani, M. F., & Farahani, F. F. (2014). The Study on Professional Ethics Components among Faculty Members in the Engineering. *Procedia: Social & Behavioral Sciences*, 116, 2085–2089. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2014.01.524>

Grant J. (2014, April). The good CPD guide. A practical guide to managed continuing professional development in medicine. PubMed Central (PMC). <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC4005177/>

Jehanzeb, K. (2012) Role of Learning Theory in the Training while Training the Trainers: *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*. Vol.2, No. 11 ISSN: 2222-6990

Kulkarni, P. P. (2013). A Literature Review on Training & Development and Quality of Work Life. *Journal of Arts, Science & Commerce: International Refereed Research Journal*, 4(2), 136. https://www.dcvmn.org/IMG/pdf/paper_20.pdf

Lacayanga, R. B. (2019, December 16). Problems encountered among teachers on RPMS: Inputs for Teachers Enhancement Program. *TeacherPH*. <https://www.teacherph.com/action-research-rpms-teachers-enhancement-program/>

Madhekeni, A. (2012). Implementing Results-Based Management Systems in Zimbabwe: Context and Implications for the Public Sector. *International Journal of Humanities and Social Science*. https://www.ijhssnet.com/journals/Vol_2_No_8_Special_Issue_April_2012/16.

Madrigal, D.V., et al., (2019). Teacher Quality in the Light of the Philippine Professional Standard for Teachers. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/332103677>

McCombes, S. (2023, June 22). Descriptive research | Definition, types, methods & examples. Scribbr. <https://www.scribbr.com/methodology/descriptive-research/>

Mohammed Saad, A. et al., (2013) Review of Theory of Human Resources Development Training (Learning) Participation: WEI International Academic Conference Proceedings.

Nairuba, J. (2021). Motivational Practices And Teachers’ Performance In Jinja : Municipality Secondary Schools, Jinja District, Uganda: Bugema University, Kampala Campus, Uganda. ERIC - Education Resources Information Center. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/ED531291.pdf>

Osam. (2021). A Study of Teacher Performance in English for Academic Purposes Course: Evaluating Efficiency. <https://doi.org/10.1177/21582440211050386>

Selvi, Kıymet. (2010). Teachers’ Competencies. *Cultura. International Journal of Philosophy of Culture and Axiology*. ERIC - Education Resources Information Center. 7. 167-175. 10.5840/cultura20107133

Spacey, J. (2023, August 6). 4 Examples of a personal development plan. <https://simplicable.com/new/personal-development-plan>

Spacey. (2018). Development Plan. <https://simplicable.com/new/personal-development-plan>

Teacher Capability Assessment Tool (TCAT). (n.d.). Faculty of Education. <https://education.unimelb.edu.au/research/projects/teacher-capability-assessment-tool-tcat>

Town, R., et.al. (2021). Self-management, self-care, and self-help in adolescents with emotional problems: a scoping review protocol. <https://10.11124/JBIES-20-00224>

Uhl-Bien, M., & Graen, G. B. (1998). Individual Self-Management: Analysis of Professionals' Self-Managing Activities in Functional and Cross-Functional Work Teams. <https://doi.org/10.2307/256912>

Yang Ching-Chow. (2015). The integrated model of core competence and core capability, Total Quality Management & Business Excellence. <https://DOI:10.1080/14783363.2013.820024>

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